

Opportunities among Black Students and Perceptions of Secondary School Attainment

¹Shoyaib Mahmud (shoyaib15-1525@diu.edu.bd)

Shoyaib Mahmud joined as UAT Support Engineer in Grameenphone Ltd. from June, 2022. He previously worked in research field while in his student life.

²Md. Sabbir Ahmed (sabbir.mt.pt@gmail.com)

Md. Sabbir Ahmed completed his Diploma in Physiotherapy from Institute Of Health Technology (IHT), Baptist Mission Road, Barishal and finished internship from Rajshahi Medical College Hospital -RMCH. Then he started studying in Bachelor of Science in Physiotherapy in Institute of Medical Technology, Mirpur12, Dhaka under Faculty of Medicine, University of Dhaka.

³Mirza MD. Tanvir Mahtab Faysal (mirzatanvir134@gmail.com)

Mirza MD. Tanvir Mahtab Faysal is a student of Economics, content writer, exBNCC cadet and former debator in DRMC Remian Debating Society. Participated in different social activities.

⁴Shadman Sakeef (srsakeef@gmail.com)

Shadman Sakeef, a student of BSc in Environmental Science and Disaster Management worked, organized, coordinated and volunteered many environment related and similar programs.

¹Graduate of CSE, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Daffodil International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

²Student of BSc in Physiotherapy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

³ Student of Bachelor of Economics in Developmental Economics, Dhaka School of Economics (DScE), University of Dhaka.

⁴Student of BSc in Environmental Science and Disaster Management in Daffodil International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Abstract

Education is an important device within the improvement of today's world. The potential to broaden oneself performs a vital position in growing destiny possibilities for individuals. This is the purpose why it's far taken into consideration essential for college students of all ethnicities, creed and values advantage good enough knowledge. However, numerous researchers have discovered that minority ethnicities in Britain be afflicted by structural disadvantages. In particular, boys of Black African and Black Caribbean background be afflicted by loss of good enough get entry to to instructional attainment and possibilities. This observe tries to hyperlink the machine in a few colleges to the failure with the aid of using Black male students.

Method Applied: The participants in the study were subjected to brief questionnaires first to gather sensitive information that most of them would be unwilling to answer openly. The questionnaires contained sets of close-ended questions making the answer time short enough and then review process easier. The process was followed by semi-structure interview session that each participant was taken through in order to inquire about various factors including

Results: It was apparent that the school system had some technical and social issues that needed working out. There was a realization that albeit being affected by other factors outside the school such as poverty and peer pressure the school system also played a significant part in the student's low attainment and expectations about opportunities. The study found institutional racism and a breakdown in the student-teacher relationship to be a major factor in lower attainment by Black boys relative to student from other ethnicities. While there is need for a more in-depth study into the findings of the results.

Conclusion: The study into how social factors affect Black boys is an essential conversation starter when discussing how students grow up to take advantage of the higher positions in the society. That teachers support ideas bordering on institutional racism even if they are not perpetrators should be a cause for reforms. Nonetheless, most schools including the one

where the study was carried out have been attempting to improve and weed out institutional racism and cultural bias. Still, such initiatives need to be expanded further.

Introduction

1.1 Statement of the problem

Education is a critical part of the United Kingdom's social, political and economic aspects of life. Over the last few years numerous law and policies have been enacted to create suitable environment for all students within the country. While the policies have provided some good results, children from minority communities still suffer disparities in their pursuit of education. This is especially true when considering how well male Black students are in comparison to students from other communities. This paper aims to establish how well secondary school education is suited to the education of Black African and Afro Caribbean male students. It also aims to review how well the education setup is with regards to Black only secondary school establishments.

Various researchers have reiterated these sentiments by showing how much Black male students or those of mixed Black heritage are disadvantaged in comparison to children from other marginalized communities. In particular Spence (2013) indicates that Black students require more opportunities due to their disadvantaged backgrounds a systematic racism follows them even after their completion of early education. This means that male Black students required adequate attention during the formative education period to help sustain their growth in upper classes.

Lack of adequate attention to male Black students has resulted in disparities among Black communities across the UK. One direct challenge arising from racial disparity in schools has been marked by failure of male Black students in their primary and high school education. Scholars have provided a number of reasons in an attempt to explain the reasons behind such failure and they provide a good review of how well the English education policy caters to the individuals from minority communities.

The study is not entirely driven by pure academic pursuits, but also, the researchers' own personal inquisitiveness. The researcher is of African heritage born of two immigrants

from Ghana. As a second-generation immigrant, his identity as a Black student was a factor in his education. Lack of proper understanding in the larger Black masculine role meant that he lacked a sense of self-esteem and was therefore influenced by his peers towards a negative direction. The effect of indulging and giving in to negative peer influence saw poor performance in secondary school. He was only able to achieve a 'D' grade as the highest mark in all of his GCSE papers. In retrospect, he has come to understand that while the Education system had its own pitfalls, he bears some personal responsibility in his secondary school failure. Nonetheless, he views the need to review the structural deficiencies in the education system as something that will provide more understanding and chance for better education to other students who have a Black heritage.

1.2 Context

The study was conducted in mixed secondary school within the London Metropolitan area. The schools has a significant population of students from other ethnicities apart from British whites. This mix is good when comparing the level of education among various ethnicities. Additionally, the students present different levels of English use. At the lower rungs are just recently arrived immigrants whose English is at the A1 beginner level while the highest in most classes may be the proficient speakers who use the language at a C1 expert level. While most of the students speak English at a C2 level, most of the immigrants spoke at either C1 or B2 level. The difference between C1 and B2 speakers mostly relied on the parents' country of origin and the length of time one had stayed in the country.

1.3 Purpose Statement and Rationale

Social bias is a problem in many marginal communities across the UK. This study seeks to review the impact of social bias and the intertwined experiences of boys from Black and Afro-Caribbean heritage towards their performance and outlook in state secondary schools. Before proceeding any further, it is worth mentioning that the use of Black Africans within this paper refers to children who were born in Africa to parents that have African

roots. Afro-Caribbean or Black Caribbean is used in reference to children with Caribbean roots or those who were born and emigrated from the Caribbean. The use of the term “Black” without any other qualification will be a reference to Blacks in general. Despite of the reality that labeling is taken into consideration a valued exercise it's far now being argued that labeling does extra damage than appropriate and inclusion programme is taken into consideration an ideal (Sakib, 2022).

The precarious situation that Black boys face in schools was recognized in OFSTED's report, which indicated that generally children from minority communities perform poorly in comparison to children from other communities (Gillborn, & Gipps, 1996). This sentiment is reiterated in an earlier study by Coard (1971), which ranked many children from Black communities as Educationally Sub-Normal.

The OFSTED's study also points out that, Black boys appear to perform far worse than Black girls and any other gendered racial group for that matter (Gillborn, & Gipps, 1996). More than two decades later, it would appear that very little has changed in favor of boys as more reports looking into the state of African heritage boys education in the US still reveal poor performance as a problem. This should act as a challenge to all stakeholders to be proactive in tackling the issue of poor education when discussion matters of boy child education. As such, this study will be carrying out a review of its terms while concentrating the study in an English school with a considerable mixed population in terms of gender and race.

1.4 Research questions

Black students are at a critical juncture in their lives, due to awareness over the structural disadvantages they face. This seems as the most appropriate time to peek into the problems associated with English education and life with regard to the education of Black male students. For this reason this study seeks to know”

- I. What are the perceptions of Black African and Caribbean Male in terms of secondary school attainment and Opportunities?
- II. What are the key factors that impact schools achievement capabilities among boys from African and Afro Caribbean communities in England?

Literature Review

2.1 History of Education of Black African and Caribbean people

The history of Black of education is fickle at best and non-existent in a worst-case scenario. Trying to retrace the history of black education in the county is a hard task and even the information is able to gather is often insufficient. The way the English education system has long been crafted to serve a particular section of the society; which is the majority white population. However, as the Black population has increased over the last 100 years, it would have been prudent to redraft the education standards to fit the needs of Black students. This includes ensuring that diversity covers areas such as history and English where Black students can feel that their indigenous cultures are appreciated. Needless to add, this is a matter that affects many other minority communities including eastern Europeans in the British state-funded education system.

Most British Black students trace their historical roots to adverse conditions such as slavery and colonization, both of which the UK took part in. in this respect, England shares a little commonality with the US. However, unlike the US, there is little in the way of historic retracing of Black history in English state schools (Palfreyman, & Smith, 2003.).

Warmington (2012) attempts to provide a reason behind the lack of proper history of African and Afro Caribbean history in the British system by pointing to the early sentiments of Blacks as outliers in the larger British societal framework. He states that:

There has long been awareness among Black British thinkers that the haphazard development of education policies designed to address the needs and experiences of Black children in British schools told a revealing story about the wider struggle to overturn perceptions of people of color as an alien problem visited upon the (white) nation

What the statement above shows is that Blacks have suffered from long held biases against their inclusion within the British education structure. As will be seen later on, boys are often at the head and tail end of most such bias.

Even small things can make impact on the overall system of a school or educational institution. For example, application of the procurement methods in the various senior high schools have an adverse impact on them instead of aiding them to achieve value for money (Sakib, 2022). Critical race theory covered in depth below, stresses how racism is a factor in the provision of key services in societies. The nub of the theory is that both racial inequality and discrimination have played a part in disrupting political, social, and economic structures in countries such as the UK and providing appropriate grounds for the mistreatment of individual based on skin colour (Wilson, Burgess, & Briggs, 2011). According to some theorists in this school, such as Zadie Smith, the racial connotation of students heavily influences their ability to gain access to equitable education (Warmington, 2012). While Smith had an emphasis on the US as study case, the same though may be applied to the UK as an integrated developed nation whose history of Blacks bear some similarities to the US. This has had an impact on how well historians were able to review and catalogue Black educational history in the country.

The lack of educational history, has a significant impact on how well Black children acquaint themselves to school. Boys, specially, show a tendency of trying to identify with their heritage from an exceptionally young age. The lack of such spaces within the school environment means that students in need of cultural validation will not feel appreciated. In

respect to this absence, they may seek to remove or sequester themselves from the education activities (Gillborn, & Drew, 2010). This explanation could help explain the differences between how whites and Blacks interact within educational settings. Moreover, the need by boys to acclimatize and identify with their heritage would explain the acquiescing of Black boys into peer groups that pose a negative influence on their academic influence.

2.2 Early and Elementary Education for Black Students

Early education is an essential part of a student's trajectory towards academic success. Therefore, it is necessary to make an enquiry on the value of early and elementary education for Black male students. While studying the influence of elementary education in the US, but targeting Black students, Boutte (2012) holds that, "One rationale for teaching during the early childhood years is that there is an opportunity to teach students while they are impressionable as opposed to the later years when the cumulative effects of nonsuccess are more difficult to reverse and erase." This means that an adequate level of teaching can instill lots of appreciation for education in a way that is insurmountable if the same is lacking.

While it is necessary to have a sufficient early background for most students to compete and relate on an equal footing, this appears to be lacking among a large percentage of young Black children. In the UK, a good percentage of all Black children come from lesser off backgrounds. According to Palmer and Kenway (2007), around 45% of Black Africans and 30% of Black Caribbeans are classified with the poorest quantity of the British population. An additional 20% of Black Africans and 22% of Black Caribbeans are classified within the lower middle-income bracket of the society. This means that most of their parents struggle to support their children through formative education where a lot of attention and economic input is required for the basic instruments.

Nonetheless, despite the challenges faced by Black students in their formative years, there are indications that they do perform considerably well during those years in comparison to children from other backgrounds. A report from OFTSED (2002) notes:

The evidence that has been available from individual LEAs has tended to show that the relative performance of Black Caribbean pupils begins high, starts to decline in Key Stage 2, tails off badly in Key Stage 3 and is below that of most other ethnic groups at Key Stage 4. (p.1)

Black Africans are not spared either, since Gillborn and Gipps (1996) note that “Black pupils generally may be falling further behind the average achievement of the majority of their peers.” Aratan, White and Cooper (2011) also reiterate the same when they note that when Black kids, especially boys, get into kindergarten, the cases of academic challenges are usually minimal, but as time passes, they tend to lose academic grounds to the white students. These two statements show that there should concern on the trajectory of achievement relative to progression into higher classes. There must be sociocultural factors that influence how students perceive their participation in classes, which further negatively impacts future opportunities.

2.3 Impact of Achievement Disparities

As earlier stated, there is the existence of disparities between Black males and white males, and this can be of a negative effect on most of the Black African students. Research conducted by the National Centre for Educational Statistics indicated that there is a possibility of many people living in poverty, especially those that are not good at reading. Also, in 2009, a report was compiled by McKinsey and Company, which showed that educational achievement gaps may be highly expensive concerning the underutilization of the workforce. It also continued to stress out that individuals that possess low academic achievement tend to get lower earnings and increased rates of work than the others. The achievement gap can also be a threat to the economic stability of the nation. In case of their achievement gap mostly between the Latinos and Black students, the GDP of the United States would drop from 525 to 310 U.S. Dollars. Some institutional policies and practices have an impact on Black African

males. It is also noted that there is a possibility of Black males being expelled or suspended three times more than other groups of people.

2.4 Critical Race Theory and Social Context Race

This theory emerged from a variety of activists and researchers that wanted to study more about race, power, and racism, and their relationship with people's behaviours (Delgado and Stefancic 2012). This theory was introduced in the mid-1970s to examine the effects of racism and race in Critical Legal Studies. In these studies, scholars were worried about the racial reform activities and establishment of conservative policies in the U.S. Over the past years, and this theory has transformed into different disciplines other than law for example in education. This theory analyses not only the people of colour but also suggest some measures on how to improve their lives in a given country (Zamudio, Russell, Rios, & Bridgeman, 2011). One of the most factors to consider in this theory is racism, which has been defined by many scholars. Racism can simply be defined as the system where white people are considered superior to other people with different backgrounds.

The social context race theory is one of the "pseudo-scientific biological theories" that is mostly used to address the issues of racism in society. It mainly focuses on the teaching of the individuals that are Black. Giroux (2011) explains more about colonization and slavery and how all these disciplines were justified by applying biological theories. It also noted that the subject of race became popular as a result of slavery that affected Black Africans due to the colour of their skin. Institutional racism is also considered but it is not easy to identify it because of its wider establishments. It is believed to originate from the institutions of larger forces and attracts low public condemnation. It is noted that this usually occurs in schools especially where teachers fail to offer a professional service to their immediate students basing on either ethnic background or colour. Different policies were established in institutional racism, which promoted equality within different schools. One of the reports known as "The Swann Report" expressed concerns about "Education for all." This was established to implement some of the

teachings from different cultures to put them in one curriculum. In his research, Swann found that racism was believed to have a "causal effect" on to the lower educational achievement (Muller, et al.2004).

Besides, another report called "The Macpherson Report" was also examined. This report majorly focused on the "Metropolitan Police Service" while examining the Stephen Lawrence case. It further suggested that National Curriculum, especially in schools, should be used as a way of appreciating cultural diversity (Virdee, 2006). The Swann report had also recommended it in 1985. It also noted that those Black Caribbean students are found to be performing worse than any other group of people. This is because Black Caribbean students are affected by institutional racism most especially in the English schools and as a result, their goal for academic success is negatively affected.

2.5 Deficit perspective of Black male

Based on the works of some scholars, it was discovered that a variety of schools carry out their operations in a deficit concerning the education of Black students, and in this case, male students are considered (Howard, Flennaugh, & Terry. 2012, p. 92). One of the scholars known as Theresa Perry (2003) explained how the minimum achievement of students and, in this case, the Black ones were directly related to the deficit perspective. In her works, she explained how people have to face the fact that Black students, with their parents and in the Black communities they lived, were to be blamed for the limited or no Black student achievement. It should also be noted that Black male students continue to work hard in schools with the perception of their struggles in the overall community. Howard (2008) identified the forms of stereotypes and some of the problems that the Black males encounter during their school time. He talked about how Black African males were amid "stereotyped notions" that are gender and race and that these notions tend to place these in unpleasant moments not only in schools but also in the community.

For the last two centuries, the history of Black males has been characterized by too much involvement in slavery, super athletes, and "hyper-sexed brute," among others. It is observed these characteristics still have an impact on the perceptions of Black males in society. Therefore, all these play a significant role in the different politics in the school environment. A term called "At-risk" is also a deficit framework used to study Black males in schools. This framework is based on the principle that Black children don't possess normative culture and values that are required to become successful in a secondary school. Since Black males are considered to be different and possess oppositional attributes concerning other normal students, this explains why the life of Black males will be difficult in schools.

Based on the literature review above focusing on the Black students in the secondary schools, the researcher identified some gaps in the literature, which must be addressed. Firstly, the relationship between Black boys and their teachers is still lacking evidence. Secondly, there is little evidence that demonstrates how Black males interact with the supplementary schools about secondary schools. It also does not talk about the impact of the curriculum of supplementary schools on Black African males. There is also little information provided about the voices of Black males of which this essay is mainly based on their views. Little evidence about youth organizations is also provided. Besides, more research should be conducted on the interaction between Black males and youth workers. Furthermore, the social influence that exists between males and youth workers should also be extensively analyzed.

2.6 Quality of Education in Schools

A variety of perceptions have been established which explain that the quality of education provided to the Black students is inadequate compared to other groups of students (Frankenberg et al 2013). This was observed in the segregated Black schools. On the contrary, with Frankenberg et al (2013), other scholars disagreed with the perception of these schools that they were ineffective. They stressed out that despite poor materials, facilities, and relevant support systems, these schools were considered to be effective regarding providing improved

and quality education not only to the white but also Black students in the region (Siddle-Walker 2005, p.765). It is also noted that there was a strong relationship between the teachers, parents, and students since all these parties were considered to be living in the same community. In these schools, teachers had personal relationships with the parents of their students. This relationship is believed to have enabled teachers to engage in strategies that support both the social and educational aspects of the student. It is also noted that in the segregated Black schools, teachers were highly familiar with students, and as a result, they had a deep understanding of the challenges faced by students. Black students dealing with Black teachers was the best opportunity they experienced because those teachers had a clear understanding of similar life experiences like dealing with racism in the communities. Many scholars agreed that the distinctive characteristics of segregated schools allowed flexibility within the education sector by promoting emotional and social support.

Based on the statistics, it is observed that the most misbehaved students in schools are Black males and that they score poorly lower than the grade level. They are characterized by involvement in fights, cutting classes, gambling, among others. It is noted that some scholars and educators have been considered to be blunt concerning the bone positive critique of the Black male students. As a result, there is a deficit thinking among the culture and community where the students stay, which makes teachers start blaming students and their parents. A study was conducted to study the way the parents perceived the environment within which their Black sons study. It was discovered that many of the participants showed that racism was the root cause of the problems and experiences of their sons. Some parents also expressed their concerns about how the school officials communicated to their sons, which was hostile compared to the white students who were treated fairly. Parents further indicated that their Black sons were affected by the micro-aggressions during their stay in schools.

Methodology

3.1 Research design

The essence of a study such as this is to provide an understanding of social influences within communities. Such studies attempt to define myths and grand narratives” and delineate them from rationality, scientific method, and certainties of the world (Merriam, 2009).” As such, this study will be classed under qualitative research. According to Bachman and Schutt (2017), the term “qualitative research suggests that “that a researcher can get a clearer picture of the social reality being studied by viewing it from several different perspectives.” It is an understanding that is derived from different perspectives that this study seeks in relation to the quality of education for Black boys in Britain. It is worth adding that this study is being conducted within a natural setting, thus adding to the need to concentrate on its qualitative bases.

When looking at how students and teachers act within their natural environment it may be hard to objectively quantify the reactions that a researcher comes across. To this extent, Bachman and Schutt (2017, indicate that “explanations developed inductively from qualitative research can feel authentic because we have heard what people have to say in their own words, and we have tried to see the social world as they see it.” The literature provided above shows how much the research derives its abilities from social interactions rather than the standard numerical experiments within labs. When dealing with individuals there is an innate derives from listening to them and being able to interpret their words in a way that will be academically relevant to the research and other future researcher who wishes to go through the paper.

It is worth remembering that the study’s unmentioned aim is reviewing social learning patterns attached to one subjects of the society. This mean reviewing education figures in to the lives of Black students in so doing, the researcher will be questioning how the society has impacted the ability of Black boys to achieve academic success or fail for that matter.

Essentially, there is a sense that the study involves looking at Black boys from the prism of oppressive pedagogy that can be traced to the education and surrounding social system. This bodes well with what Bachman and Schutt (2018) mean when they state that;

“members of marginalized groups are better positioned than members of socially dominant groups to describe the ways in which the world is organized according to the oppressions they experience.”

This they note is part of the reason why qualitative research is an important part of many research discourses since it emphasizes “emphasizes the need for recognizing that what is understood by participants as reality is only a social construction of reality (Bachmann, & Schutt, 2018).” The researcher in this study adopts this stance.

3.1.1 Phenomenological case study approach

The structural references attached to educational achievement and the opportunities derived in this study mark various phenomena. For instance, with regard to this study institutional racism was expected to play a crucial part in the reduced achievement of Black boys. This marks a phenomenon within a larger context. As such, this study bears the success of its results in the phenomenological case study approach that it embraces. According to Crawford (2016), “phenomenological research allows one to understand the essence of a human experience in order to gain a rich understanding of a particular experience from the perspective of the participant.” This is one of the most powerful approaches when studying actual day-to-day experiences.

Case studies focus on everyday happenings as would and should be viewed casually on street levels. Research can expect to gain intuitive value by using case studies in their sociological investigations (Merriam, 2009). The researcher views this sentiment as a key factor in the reasoning behind the use of case study in this study. By using case studies, researchers are able to not only derive, but also self-assess their own understanding of the

phenomenon under study (Alase, 2017). A failure to realise how the various factors under study figure within the larger context under study may be considered a challenge when dealing with other studies but in the case of a phenomenological study, it is possible to gain further understanding that helps reduce research bias.

This study relied on the OFSTED's definition of secondary schools grades to prepare the foundation on which the researcher would carry out investigations. The researcher considered it prudent to concentrate the search on one school with a substantial population of white and Black students. Additionally, the chosen school already had an adequate number of both Black Africans and Black Caribbean students. A more refined focus delineating the discussion of the study from a larger field was deemed essential in creating a critical appeal to readers and reviewers of the research. The researcher chose a funnel-oriented approach of questioning which Flick (2017), identifies as working "systematically from less structured, open-ended questions to more complex, structured, open-ended questions.

3.1.2 Pros and Cons of a case study

Case studies carry with them significant advantages and disadvantages which need elaboration in this paper. A notable advantage attached to the use of case studies is the transfer of the knowledge from one section of scholars to another. Stake (2005), notes that there are several learning approaches to be gleaned in on from the sharing of stories across various social strata in cases studies. One may think of social studies as a tradition where individuals provide their own experience with a particular phenomenon for other to learn from. This is especially important when the idea under discussion borders ideas only understood by minority sections of the society.

For a better understanding of the point above one may have to think of the rigidity found in traditional studies. Such studies tend to try and place a preconceived notion of the society upon the subject forming the participant base. This results in a loss of truth and reliability in the study and also creates an imbalance in the relevance of studies to the public

(Bachman, & Schutt, 2013). The current study should focusing on ensuring that there is enough and proper preparation of information for other scholars and interested general audience to gain information from the paper.

Flexibility is another factor that is considered important in the discussion on the relevance of case studies. Discussions on Blacks and ethnic minorities within a the educational context often reflects the difficulty of accepting their unique disadvantaged position in the society (Shaw, Atvars, Humphrey, & Sims, 2017). Participants may deem it important to review and even withhold responses to certain questions that they view as offensive, personal or not relevant to the studies breach. Phenomenological cases studies provide a flexible approach to filling in the gaps associated with improper approaches of education.

3.2 Sampling

For a proper understanding of the factors under study, the researcher collected data from a number of students in the chosen school. The data collection process was enabled by the use of purposive sampling. Uwe Flick (2017), notes that “many purpose sampling strategies ... require prior knowledge about the phenomenon in question and its distribution.” This statement explains why the researcher chose to depend on purposive sampling for the study. As an individual who has a background with most of the participants it was easy to choose relevant areas to look into rather than simply depending on lighter areas that most other studies looking to the matter have delved into.

As part of the study's measures, the researcher is binding the students under review to their Black heritage and male gender. On the other hand, the teaching population was well suited to having a mixture of various cultural backgrounds. This helped reveal the different normative responses in the student-teacher relationship. Since this is a study that seeks to question experiences as a concept in attainment/achievement and opportunities, taking into account the raw responses is particularly important (Gillborn , 1997; Richardson, 2015).

There is a dearth of sufficient information in this area because studies into Black secondary education attainment are more recent and thus the value of raw responses as intimated above cannot be understated.

For this study the researcher chose to work on set of 30 students aged between 15 and 17 from three different classes. All these students were of Black heritage from the wider Black African and Caribbean Black groups. Their teachers were also slotted into the study to provide the alternative more mature response on how racial ties impact the students' ability to attain proper marks. While the researcher considered it important to include parents into the study as well, this was deemed hard due to various factors including the unwillingness by parents to actively participate in the study. However, parents to five of the students provided some assistance with regards to their parental participation role in the education of their children.

The core bases for the researcher included identifying the attitude that both teachers and students hold of each other and education, the approaches to academic achievement, and a realization of how each of the targeted subject quarters responses to factors associated with Black boys academic success. The motivation and active status of each groups with regards to the education of Black students was also questioned in the course of the study. An anticipation was made that students, irrespective of their gender or ethnicity have a willingness to succeed. Additionally, a general assumption was made before sampling that teachers would have goodwill to support their students' success. However, the attempts to push their students towards success would be reduced by negative social influence that is nurtured through family and larger social backgrounds.

Although the researcher would have loved to tout case studies as the elixir of social studies, that is not entirely true. One of the disadvantages of trying to use cases studies is that the investigator is expected to serve as the primary instrument in the collection and analysis of data (Bachman, & Schutt, 2013). This may be challenging where the researcher is juggling

various other duties as often happens with most scholars including pure academic scholars. This is a challenge that the researcher in this study understands because it had a personal impact on his ability to work and provide quality-based results. Nonetheless, there are no two ways out since the researcher needs to invest adequate input into their work.

Another problem that researchers often face in case studies is the tendency by subjects to alter their behavior. Change in behavior, as little as may be observed can have a great impact on behavioral studies since every aspect of interactions counts to the results and perceptions (Yin, 2015). What Yin (2015) intimates is very relevant to this study. For instance, teachers may temper any negative comments they prefer to students when another adult and a researcher for that matter is in class. There will be a tendency to try and place themselves in good light. The lack of observance of any negative practices may lead the researcher to assume that a student's bad attitude towards a teacher is unwarranted.

Selection bias is also something that is associated with case studies. Researchers in cases studies tend to choose participants how fit a particular narrative that they would wish to portray (Merriam, 2009). This ends up creating homogeneity of responses which may not be reflective of real case scenarios or a representation of the whole spectra in real life. For instance, knowingly choosing boys who have grown up under the parentage of single mothers is likely to yield a similarity of thoughts towards a particular direction. This type of research skewing is discouraged and adequate measures need to be taken to ensure that it does not occur within the bounds of their research.

3.3 Data collection

Multiple sources of the research were applied to arrive at an appropriate level of research depth. Since this is a phenomenological case study, it was appropriate to use different forms for data sourcing in a way that increases the validity and credibility of the paper. The study relied on a mix of questionnaires and interviews for a suitable measure of validity.

3.3.1 Questionnaires

The data collection process began with the issuing out of questionnaires to all students targeted under the study. The questionnaires contained close-ended questions that were easy and fast to tick against. This ensured that there would be very little time spent answering questions as normally happens in the case of open-ended questionnaires. The students were also assured that there is no right or wrong answer in the questionnaire in order to dispel any attempts to want to sound correct which might also mar the correctness of the results. To improve on the results and create a sense of anonymity, the students were asked not to write their names on the paper or put in any identifying marks that may be traced back to them.

3.3.2 Semi-structured interviews

The second step was carrying out a brief interview that involved the use of structured open-ended questions and semi-structured questions in the review process. The students were subjected to a couple of questions meant to cover areas that the initial paper would have barely covered. The approach for this particular task was getting each student on their own in a one-on-one conversation. The tone used was relaxed in order to put them at ease in the course of the interview. Personal experience of the writer was used to bear familiarity with the students' experiences. This was in a bid to show the students that the researcher understood where they were coming from. Nonetheless, the researcher took adequate measure to ensure that his interjections did not mar the trajectory of the interview.

The teachers were also subjected to an analysis of how well they respond to the needs of the students given the unique challenges that Black students often go through. The key areas of concern was their attitudes towards their students, the ability to offer enough learning opportunities to the students, task handling and ability to take advantage of personal, social and cultural background that most of the students find themselves in. this was done using a set of shorter questionnaires than that which the students were subjected to.

Additionally, they were subjected to a shorter interview sessions to provide a sense of validity in the paper. The parents were also subjected to a similar process.

Some other sources of data used in this study include various OFSTED documents that provided a depth of understanding over what the researcher was looking into. Additionally various reposts on the value of secondary schools education helped set a basis upon which the researcher could line up questions without running afoul of the participants. There was an emphasis on the knowledge gap found in most of these documents as the first port of call. Nonetheless, there was also need to conform to what these documents had since most of them were sanctioned by various relevant authorities over the years.

Analysis and results

4.1 Introduction

Data analysis and interpretation in qualitative research is conducted with the purpose of providing opportunities to air and deduce the narratives from studies contributors. Observers may be in a rush to interpret their results using their own biased means. Nonetheless, a retrospective data analysis assures the reader that the results were carried out in a balanced manner (Auerbach, & Silverstein, 2003). This is an essential part of all well planned and balanced out studies. Merriam (2009) notes that “without ongoing analysis, the data can be unfocused, repetitious, and overwhelming in the sheer volume of material that needs to be processed. Data that have been analysed while being collected are both parsimonious and illuminating.” Therefore, data analysis can be viewed as a result of the need to engender a sense of above-board research in academic work.

4.2 Data analysis

This research analysis process began by analysing the documents that the researcher had at hand. OFSTED ethnic representations in schools was the first important that that the researcher looked into. This helped derive an image of how far the researchers sampling was from the national averages. Moreover, an analysis of UK government website on ethnic

balance in education also provided a critical point of analysing the way teachers are distributed vis-à-vis the balance of students across different schools. This information was needed to analyse if the chosen school reflected national and even regional representation of teachers

The data from the semi-structured interviews, which had been digitally recorded, was analysed and transcribed for ease of access in legible form. All the information was analysed and transcripts arranged according to the classification of the study's participants as well as the identifying features. Codification of the data was identified as a necessary step in lightening the amount of work involved in analysing the data.

4.3 Ethical considerations

This study was looking into a relatively controversial subject bordering on institutional racism and bias. As such, it was necessary to take adequate measures not to anger the participants. Secondly, the study involved children and parental consent was sought. Additionally, the children were taken through the demands of the research and reassured of their privacy and anonymity. They were also assured that they could withdraw from the study at any point in time. All participants were informed of how the data collected would be used and reassured that there would be no reference to their person or linking a particular response to a single response.

Findings

5.1 Interactions between teacher and students

The researcher's gauging of interactions between teachers and their students yielded some interesting results. It is worth noting that there are so many social factors affecting how students perceive education; a critical factor is the relationship between students and their teachers (Cook, et al., 2018). The study attempted to look into how this factor figures in the perception male Black secondary school students.

The relationship between teachers and their students often correspond to the value of cultural pedagogy where the teacher as the instructor bears more control while the student is expected to play a subservient role in class (Giroux, 2011). This makes it hard for students to interact with their teachers on a partnership basis. The study found that 63% of the responding teachers held the notion of the teacher as the leader in classroom and the students as passive participants. This notion is also reflected in the dedication of the teachers towards the success of their students. The researcher was able to review the results of the students relative to the teachers. He noted that there were marginal higher performances in classes with a collaborative teaching approach. This reflection catered for all students including Black Africans and Black Caribbean students.

More concerning were stereotypical attitudes that are derived from lack of understanding in the culture and traditions of other students. All students noted that they had experience with mislabeling of their culture. In one instance, a third generation UK Black student was quizzed about conditions in Zimbabwe, a country that both his British-Born parents had only visited once. Another common stereotype associated with the teaching of Blacks is that most boys grow up rude and with a penchant for violence (Demie, & Mclean, 2017). 60% of the female teachers interviewed indicated that they found it needless to engage male Black students who were indisciplined. Instead, they would refer such cases to male teachers or the administration to handle. This was in contrast to 80% of cases where a teacher sought to intervene and assist a white student before escalating any further cases to higher authorities or colleague assistance. One teacher explicitly mentioned that she was “*afraid of getting physically abused by Black students*”, despite never having undergone such a scenario or knowing anyone close who had gone through such an encounter.

The study also revealed that the stereotype attached to the allowance to participate in class. There appeared to be an innate need to curtail male Black students’ participation in classes by teachers. All the interviewed Black students indicated that they had experience

with biased allowance to participate. One student was asked *to concentrate his efforts in basketball, because that was the only place he never joked around*. This is despite being in a class of many athletes and relatively performing higher than them. 40% of students acknowledged that they had faced a teacher in their class with biased allowance, providing White and Asian students more participatory chances. All the students interviewed indicated that participatory bias was a sufficient cause for lack of focus in education. This was also reflected in the performance rates; in the stunted performance across various subjects. One noted that, *“although English is my favorite subjected and I have previously won awards in essay writing, my teacher always believes that I can’t write any better than I speak (with a twang).”* An analysis of the performance results across different classes showed that the classes that the students had indicated as having structurally biased teachers recorded general poor results. Nonetheless, the performance was not low across board but reflective of high performance among the race that was favored. On the other hand, pedagogically controlled classes where the teacher was identified as lacking bias registered low grades across board.

5.2 Institutional racism

Institutional racism is another important aspect in the subject since the core of the subject is about Black students; a minority group in the state-funded education system. Demie and Mclean (2017) note that “Black Caribbean pupils are often excluded for challenging what is racism, teachers’ low expectations and institutional racism.” Similarly, Black African students suffer from exclusion as a result of institutional racism.” This occurrence appears to be the case in the classes that were involved in the study.

In the study, institutional racism was looked into with the results showing that teachers were susceptible to perpetrating incidence of racial bias. Most of the discussion in the teacher-student relationship section borders on institutionalised racism. For instance, approximately 44% of the interviewed teachers indicated that they had no problem with another teacher indicating that Black students had a predisposition to rudeness and violence.

This is despite no cases of the violence being reported in the school. One teacher simply stated to the observer, “*without wishing to be offensive, blacks live through adversity and they grow rude from a young age to defend themselves.*” Coincidentally, all the teachers who reported fearing violence were non-Black. On the other hand, the interviewed Black teachers noted that they would be offended by such sentiments.

Additionally, only 65% of teachers indicated that they were willing to intervene in cases where extraneous factors beyond academic linked factor were affecting the performance of students. On the other hand, 75% of all the Black students interviewed indicated that they appreciated having teachers intervening in extraneous factors including family-related issues. 80% of the students indicated that they were more comfortable having teachers intervening in issues instead of having social workers or members of the administration intervening. The alternative was viewed as creating more negative relationships between the students and their minders thus negatively influencing their education.

5.3 Differentials in performance

While this study has largely looked at the performance of Black boys as a single set, the performance of this group was also reviewed according to the different ethnic backgrounds. However, Sewell (1997) notes that there are disparities between the attainment levels of Black Africans and Afro-Caribbean with Black Africans showing a more positive performance.

The average rate of performance appears to go against some factors such as poverty rates where Black African report higher rates (Tomlin, Wright, & Mocombe, 2014). In the study, most Black African showed an almost similar enthusiasm level in attainment during the observation process. During the interview session, 605 percent of the teachers indicated that Black Africans “*were more open to new ideas.*” This phrase was explicitly used by three teachers and the concept was repeated in different words by other teachers. This may reflect a

shared opinion, but may also be a real observation. Nonetheless, the performance results observed by the researcher indicated that students were performing poorly by between 5% and 10% on average. The higher the perception of pedagogy and bias from the class, the higher the attainment disparity between Black Africans and Black Caribbeans.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

This study was conducted in a state secondary school by a researcher with limited resources. Lack of resources hampered an intensive study. Additionally, lack of trust between the participants and the researcher may have resulted in muffled responses, which would affect the results. Thus, while the researcher chose to use uncontroversial questions even simple questions on the state of education may have been subject to protective and subjective bias. These are areas that any future researcher into the topic using a similar technique to be wary of. Additionally, this research can be expanded to cover other minority ethnic groups because they also face their own challenges which may be different but significant to their general state of education. Where possible, a similar research should be carried from a covert participant base to avoid shielded/muted responses.

Conclusions

As had already been intimated from the literatures review section, bias is a key challenge in the provision of quality education. This is especially true in the case of Black students. This is irrespective of their backgrounds. First, it is important to understand that boys in secondary schools are very conscious of their environment. They are within an age where they are able to grasp social nuances and respond to social cues (Fergus, 2017). Thus, when faced with bias from older people that they look up to (or are supposed to), they may hold back. This may explain the dip in performances as the student moves upwards.

Teachers have been identified as a crux of the problem because most of the time they are the purveyors of bias within schools. This implies that that there is need to redefine the terms of engagement between teachers and their students. It may be necessary to include a

sense of cultural understanding in teachers during their training to ensure that they are capable of handling student from other ethnic backgrounds other than their own. The challenge with trying to do this is that it might seem that there is a forced pacification of one's own identities. However, it is important to reiterate that the Britain has largely grown into a multicultural society and teachers have a great role to promote this value.

Another major factor in this discussion was how institutional racism warps in the discussion. Most of the actions that students undergo in schools are normally based on racial stereotypes. Most of the teachers noted as holding biases could hardly take notice of their action as racial in nature. As such, they might have even carried out their actions without notice of then impact it has on their students. On the other hand, the students noted that they were not impressed by the negative actions and as such attempted to act against them. Because of the rebuttal, the teachers may have thought of their students as rude.

References

- Alase, A. (2017). The Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA): A Guide to a Good Qualitative Research Approach. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 5(2), 9-19.
- Aratani, Y., Wight, V.R. and Cooper, J.L. (2011). Racial gaps in early childhood: Socioemotional Health, developmental, and educational outcomes among African American Boys. *National Center for Children in Poverty*, 1- 20.
- Bachman, R., & Schutt, R. K. (2013). *The practice of research in criminology and criminal justice*. Sage.
- Boutte, G. S. (2012). Urban schools: Challenges and possibilities for early childhood and elementary education. *Urban Education*, 47(2), 515-550.
- Coard, B. (1971). Making black children subnormal in Britain. *Integrated Education: Race and Schools*, 9(5), 49-52.
- Cook, C. R., Duong, M. T., McIntosh, K., Fiat, A. E., Larson, M., Pullmann, M. D., & McGinnis, J. (2018). Addressing discipline disparities for Black male students: Linking

- malleable root causes to feasible and effective practices. *School Psychology Review*, 47(2), 135-152.
- Delgado, R and Stefancic, J. (2012). *Critical race theory: An introduction*. New York, NY: New York Press.
- Demie, F., & McLean, C. (2017). *Black Caribbean Underachievement in Schools in England*. Schools' Research and Statistics Unit, Lambeth Education and Learning.
- Fantuzzo, J., LeBoeuf, W., Rouse, H., and Chen, C. (2012). Academic achievement of African American boys: A city-wide community-based investigation of risk and resilience. *Journal of School Psychology*, 50(2012), 559-579.
- Fergus, E. (2017). The integration project among white teachers and racial/ethnic minority youth: Understanding bias in school practice. *Theory into Practice*, 56(3), 169-177.
- Flick, U. (Ed.). (2017). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative data collection*. Sage.
- Frankenberg, E., Lee, C., and Orfield, G. 2013. A multiracial society with segregated schools: Are we losing the dream? K-12 Integration and Diversity. Available at: <<https://escholarship.org/uc/item/3rh7w18g>> [Accessed May. 4, 2020]
- Gillborn, D. (1997). Ethnicity and educational performance in the United Kingdom: Racism, ethnicity, and variability in achievement. *Anthropology & Education Quarterly*, 28(3), 375-393.
- Gillborn, D., & Gipps, C. (1996). *A review of recent research on achievement by minority ethnic pupils*. London: Institute of Education.
- Gillborn, D., & Drew, D. (2010). Academy exclusions. *Runnymede Trust Quarterly Bulletin*, 362, 12-13.
- Giroux, H.A. (2011). *On critical pedagogy*. New York: Continuum
- Howard, T.C., Flenbaugh, T.K., and Terry, C.L. (2012). Black males, social imagery, and the Disruption of pathological identities: Implications for research and teaching. *Educational Foundations*, 26(1-2), 85-102.
- Merriam, S.B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Muller, J. Davies, B. and Morais A. (2004). *Reading Bernstein, researching Bernstein*. London, Uk: Routledge Falmer.
- Palmer, G., & Kenway, P. (2007). Poverty rates among ethnic groups in Great Britain. *York:*

Joseph Rowntree Foundation.

- Palfreyman, D., & Smith, R. C. (Eds.). (2003). *Learner autonomy across cultures*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Richardson, J. T. (2015). The under-attainment of ethnic minority students in UK higher education: what we know and what we don't know. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 39(2), 278-291.
- Sakib, S. N. (2022). LABELING DOES MORE HARM THAN GOOD & INCLUSION IS AN IDEAL PROGRAMME.
- Sakib, S. (2022, April 8). ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF PROCUREMENT METHODS IN PUBLIC SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS IN GHANA: A CASE STUDY OF AGOGO STATE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL. <https://doi.org/10.35542/osf.io/rmbsf>
- Shaw, C., Atvars, T., Humphrey, O., & Sims, S. (2017). Who they are and how to engage them: A summary of the REACT systematic literature review of the 'hard to reach' in higher education. *Journal of Educational Innovation, Partnership and Change*, 3(1), 51-64.
- Sewell, T. (1997). *Black Masculinities and Schooling. How Black Boys Survive Modern Schooling*. London, UK: Trentham Books Ltd.
- Siddle-Walker, V. (2005). African American teaching in the south: 1940-1960. *Educational Research Journal*, 38(4), 751-779.
- Spence, L. K. (2012). The neoliberal turn in Black politics. *Souls*, 14(3-4), 139-159.
- Tomlin, C., Wright, C., & Mocombe, P. C. (2014). A structural approach to understanding Black British Caribbean academic underachievement in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Social Sciences for Policy Implications, American Research Institute for Policy Development*, 2014, 37-58.
- Virdee, S. (2006). Race, Employment and Social Change: A Critique of Current Orthodoxies. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, pp. 605-28.
- Warmington, P. (2012). 'A tradition in ceaseless motion': critical race theory and Black British intellectual spaces. *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 15(1), 5-21.
- Wilson, D., Burgess, S., & Briggs, A. (2011). The dynamics of school attainment of England's ethnic minorities. *Journal of Population Economics*, 24(2), 681-700.

Yin, R.K. (2015). *Case study research: Design and methods* (4th ed.) Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage

Zamudio, M. M, Russell, C, Rios, F.A., & Bridgeman, J. L. (2011). *Critical race theory matters: Education and ideology*. New York, NY: Routledge

Appendices

Action item checklist

Action item	Discussion summary	Completion Dates
Scheduling of activities	Creation of an adequate plan to assist in scheduling activities in line with the course demands	{Enter appropriate dates} (1 day)
Review of source documents	Reviewing whether the source documents are adequate to support the research	{Enter appropriate dates} (3 days)
Sampling	Analysis of the samples collected to ensure they meet the criteria set in the book	{Enter appropriate dates} (1 day)
Data collection	This refers to the period within which the data is set to be collected	{Enter appropriate dates} (2 days)
Analysis and presentation of data	Preparation of report in a manner that is understandable and in line with the academic demands	{Enter appropriate dates} (2 weeks)
Review of findings	Analysis over whether the findings fits with pre-planned expectations	{Enter appropriate dates} (2 weeks)

Appendix 1: Ethnic Representation Table of Participants

Group Participants	Number of interviewees	Black	White	Other ethnicities	Black Africans	Black Caribbean	Female	Male
Teachers	15	2	10	3	-	-	11	4
Student	50	30	10	10	16	14	-	-

Appendix 2: Combined responses from students

Factor	Affirmative response	Negative response
Proportion of Black students reporting experience of bias in class participation allowance	100%	0
Proportion of white students reporting experience of bias in class participation allowance	20%	80%
Proportion of all interviewed Black students that appreciated teachers intervening in extraneous factors; including family-related issues	75%	25%
Proportion of Black students comfortable having teachers intervening in issues instead of social workers or school administration	80%	20%

Appendix 2: Combined responses from students

Factor	Affirmative response	Negative response
Perception of teacher as leader instead of partner (restrictive pedagogy approach)	63%	47%
Proportion of teachers considering it appropriate to deal with Black male student issues	40%	60%
Proportion of female teachers considering it appropriate to deal with white male student issues	65%	35%
Proportion of teachers problem with another teacher indicating that Black students had a predisposition to rudeness and violence	44%	56%
Proportion of teachers willing to intervene in cases where extraneous factors beyond academic factors affecting the performance of students	55%	45%

Appendix 4: 2015 OFSTED results of student at KS2 and GCSE levels by ethnicity

Ethnicity	Average Attainment at KS2 level	Average Attainment at GCSE
Bangladeshi	81.5	60.5
Black African	79	52.5
Black Caribbean	73	41
Chinese	86.5	75.5
Indian	81.5	64.5
Pakistani	75	48.5
White British	73.5	44.5
White Other	69	46.5
All Pupils	77.375	54.1875

Source: Demie and Mclean, 2017

Appendix 5: Student/ Teacher Consent form

I _____ being of sound mind on this day _____ do agree to participate in this research study.

I understand that I can willingly withdraw or refuse to answer questions asked at any time without suffering any repercussions.

I have been appraised verbally and in written form what the study is all about and what is expected of me.

I have been provided the opportunity to ask questions before the study commences

I have been assured of the researcher's cooperation if I have any additional questions should I have nay in the course or after the study.

I have been assured that the information collected will be treated confidentially and securely I am aware that there is no monetary gain from participating in this study.

I understand that I can withdraw my responses from being included in the research even after the research has been concluded.

I hereby provide the researcher permission to use my responses in a responsible manner towards forming an interpretation in this study

Participant's Signature

Signature of participant

Date

Participant's Signature

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Signature of researcher

Date

Appendix 5: Participant Information Sheet 1. Invitation

You are invited to participate in this research project. This sheet provides important information pertaining to your invitation. You should carefully read it and ask questions on any area that is not well covered or that appears to be lacking.

2. Project's purpose

This study intends to question the state of black education in your school and its effectiveness. Your organisation has been identified as a good port for a pilot study on this area.

3. Your participative role

As a student/teacher, you have been chosen for the value you and knowledge base you represent. Your participation is not meant to victimise you or set you up for targeting. As such these questions have been crafted in an uncontroversial manner. You do not have to take part in the study either.

4. What happens if you take part?

You will be subjected to a questionnaire with around eight questions. The questions covers various aspects of education in your school. The questionnaire is standardised to fit all the respondents.

5. Negative anticipations

There should be no negative repercussions of taking part in this study. To further protect you from any negative consequences, the responses will only be viewed and analysed by the researcher. Your response shall not be subject to the organisation's review.

6. Recording policy

This study only uses a questionnaire for data collection. Participant should not expect to have their voices recorded. However, should it be deemed necessary to record a participant, then their express consent will be sought first and the same confidentiality applied to the questionnaires will apply to protect their identity.

7. Publishing

The result from all participants in the study will be collected, analysed and presented in the published report. There will be no mention of a particular participant's response. No identification of a participant can be made in the report. Should an employee wish to get the final report they can ask to be included in the circulation list.

Student questionnaire sample

1. Please indicate you parent's ethnic background in either African black, Afro-Caribbean or a mixture of both.
2. Were you born in the UK or immigrated to the UK?
3. What was your last grade in you English?
4. Do you believe that your skin colour has an effect on how some of the teachers treat?
If yes, is there more bias or appreciation of your skin?
5. Are you ever questioned about your first language or your parents/ancestral culture?
6. Do you find yourself having to translate certain English words to your parents?
7. Do you consider having had enough discussion opportunity in class?
8. Is there a class that you consider the teacher to have been harsh towards you? If yes, which one?

9. If the answer above was a yes, was the harsh treatment only tailored towards one specific area of the class?
10. If you were asked to change anything about the whole instruction system in your classes what would you propose be changed.

Teacher's Questionnaire sample

1. Which subject(s) do you teach?
2. Do you see you role as leader or a partner in class?
3. What is your thoughts about a student who talks back at you? What is your most appropriate response?
4. How far should a teacher go in intervening in a student's personal life?
5. In your classes, do you see ethnic differences as cause of learning challenges?
6. Does ethnic difference play a role in the interaction between teachers and students; not necessarily in your class.
7. Have you ever been spited in class because of ethnic difference? If yes, we would appreciate a brief narrative.
8. Do you think your school has systemic issues with institutional racism?

Interview protocols

1. What is your idea of what being black means to student?
2. What are your future aspirations after you finish school ?
3. As a follow-up to the last question what informs your desire to be (whatever the respondent hat mentioned)
4. Do you think that schools such as yours have duty to promote multiculturalism?
5. How much of an alternative culture apart from British culture are you aware of?
6. The education standards in the UK have been increasing over time, do you believe this statement covers black students?

7. Black youth are often associated with violence, do you think this statement is true?
8. Have you or anyone close to you ever been subject to violence in school setting by a black youth?
9. What adequate measures should be taken to bring ethnic minorities standard of education to par with those of students from white backgrounds?